

Reuse of untreated reactive dyeing wastewater for reactive coloration of cotton

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Textile coloration, Reactive dye, Dyeing wastewater, Recycling and reuse, Circular economy; Environment and sustainability.

ABSTRACT

Textile wastewater contains a wide range of hazardous dyes and chemicals released during pretreatment, dyeing, printing, and finishing processes, leading to significant environmental and health concerns. Among textile fibers, cotton is the most widely used, and more than half of it is dyed with reactive dyes. However, nearly 60% of these dyes remain unexhausted in the dye bath, along with substantial amounts of residual chemicals such as salts and alkalis. Although the unused reactive dyes become hydrolyzed, the remaining chemicals and water still offer considerable potential for reuse, which could reduce freshwater consumption as well as chemical usage and ETP operating costs. To evaluate this potential, untreated reactive dyeing wastewater was directly reused for cotton coloration. Wastewater collected from textile mills was assessed, and its dyeing fusibility was examined through three approaches: (i) cotton was dyed using the collected untreated wastewater with the addition of fresh dyes and chemicals according to the standard recipe to replace freshwater; (ii) only fresh dyes were added to the untreated wastewater, and dyeing was performed without auxiliary chemicals to determine the effectiveness of the residual chemicals; and (iii) based on the performance of these residual chemicals, the amounts of dyes and auxiliaries were further optimized. The dyed samples were then analyzed for shade characteristics and serviceability properties. Based on the color yield and fastness results, the study concludes that reactive dyeing wastewater can be directly reused for reactive coloration. However, repeated reuse may adversely affect dyeing levelness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Water is the most crucial and limited resource on earth, mandatory for both flora & fauna. However, the excessive use by humans in urban, industrial, and agricultural applications is causing freshwater scarcity and is already appearing in different countries [1]. With the

increasing population of the world, domestic, industrial, and agricultural wastewater are generating more, while industrial influents are contributing the major amount to global pollution [2]. Among them, textile industries are the pioneers in producing densely polluted high-volume wastewater due to the excessive use of hazardous chemicals and synthetic dyes [3-4].

Allègre and co-workers reported that the processing of 1 kg of cotton consumes nearly 70–150 L of water, 0.6 to 0.8 kg of salt, and 30 to 60 g of dyestuff, and an average-sized textile mill having a capacity of only 8 tons/day consumes 1.6 million liters per day [5-6]. After processing, this wastewater contains various pollutants, including unexhausted hydrolyzed synthetic dyes, unused auxiliary chemicals like salt, soda, finishing agents, etc., and sometimes traces of metals, leading to high BOD and COD of textile influent [7-9]. Due to the higher amount of pollutants in the textile wastewater, it is also challenging to treat and costly.

To reduce wastewater generation from the textile industry, several waterless textile processing techniques, such as supercritical carbon dioxide ($SC - CO_2$) dyeing, air-dyeing, plasma dyeing, and electrochemical dyeing, are being developed [10-11]. However, their suitability is still limited to the lab scale [12]. On the other hand, low-cost treatments of textile wastewater, like biosorbent-based adsorption, ion exchange methods, anaerobic biodegradation, etc., are also getting priority, but those have a minimum cost and some technical disadvantages [13-14]. In this circumstance, the reuse and recycling of textile wastewater will be the most suitable solution, which has already drawn global researchers' attention [15-19].

Textile wastewater, specifically dyeing wastewater, has the potential to reduce dyeing costs by reusing it because, after dyeing, the residual dye bath contains unexhausted dyes and chemicals [20]. By re-adjusting the concentration of the remaining dyes and chemicals to the required amount, this wastewater can be reused for dyeing again. Thus, by reusing the residual dye bath or dyeing wastewater, we can lower the consumption of water, chemicals, and energy, as well as reduce the influent treatment costs [21]. So two approaches can be considered for reusing dyeing wastewater in textile coloration: (i) the residual dyes and chemicals can be reused in subsequent dyeing by determining and re-adjusting the concentration by adding fresh dyes and chemicals, and (ii) the reuse of dyeing wastewater instead of freshwater if the dyes or chemicals concentration are negligible.

Regarding reactive coloration of cotton, it can contain approximately 20-50% dye [3], and the remaining dye becomes unexhausted and hydrolysed. These hydrolysed dyes have no

affinity to cotton and no chance to be reused directly by adjusting the concentration [22], while leftover chemicals, mainly salt and soda, can be reused. Moreover, reactive dyeing wastewater can be used directly as an alternative to freshwater because it contains hydrolysed reactive dyes, which have little or no impact on dyeing, and the alkaline condition is favourable for reactive coloration. However, some researchers suggested the removal of this hydrolysed dye from the water before reuse because it causes poor fastness properties of the new samples [21], [23].

The main objectives of this study are to (i) find out the feasibility of direct reusing of reactive dyeing wastewater for reactive coloration of cotton with additional dyes and chemicals, (ii) understand the reactivity of residual chemicals like salt and soda for cotton coloration, and (iii) the reactivity of residual hydrolyzed dyes on cotton. The color difference (ΔE) and color fastness properties of freshwater reactive dyed samples and reactive dyeing wastewater reactive dyed samples indicate the potentiality of direct reusing of reactive dyeing wastewater for reactive coloration of cotton.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

2.1.1 Fabric

Commercially scoured-bleached 100% cotton knitted single jersey fabric with an areal density of 160 g/m^2 is used in this investigation. The geometrical properties included course per inch (CPI) = 54, wales per inch (WPI) = 36, stitch length = 2.72 mm and yarn count 28 Ne. The fabric was collected from Renaissance Apparels Ltd., Mirzapur, Gazipur, Bangladesh.

2.1.2 Dyes

Synozol Yellow K_3 RS, Synozol Red K_3 BS, and Synozol Navy Blue KBF reactive dyes in commercial grade were collected from Kyung-In Synthetic Corporation (KISCO) and used for dyeing cotton in various conditions during this investigation.

2.1.3 Chemicals

Soda ash, glauber's salt, wetting agent, sequestering agent, levelling agent, and acetic acid were purchased from Merck, India. Table 1 represents the CAS registry number, supplier, and purity of the chemicals used in this experiment.

Table 2.1 CAS registry number, suppliers, and purity of the chemicals

Chemicals/reagents	CAS registry no	Suppliers	Purity
<i>Synozol Yellow K₃RS (Reactive Yellow 145)</i>	93050-80-7	<i>KISCO, Korea</i>	Commercial grade
<i>Synozol Red K₃BS (Reactive Red 195)</i>	93050-79-4	<i>KISCO, Korea</i>	Commercial grade
<i>Synozol Navy Blue KBF (Reactive Blue 222)</i>	93051-44-6	<i>KISCO, Korea</i>	Commercial grade
<i>Soda ash</i>	497-19-8	<i>Merck, India</i>	99.5%
<i>Glauber's salt</i>	15124-09-1	<i>Sateri, China</i>	98%
<i>Acetic acid</i>	64-19-7	<i>Merck, India</i>	99%
<i>Wetting agent</i>	11004-30-8	<i>Sarex, India</i>	99%
<i>Sequestering agent</i>	64-17-5	<i>Sarex, India</i>	99%
<i>Levelling agent</i>	63148-62-9	<i>Sarex, India</i>	99%
<i>ISO detergent</i>	N/A	<i>SDC, UK</i>	N/A

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Dyeing

In a 1:10 M:L ratio, commercially scoured-bleached 100% cotton knitted single jersey fabric dyeing was carried out in an exhaust dyeing machine (XIAMEN RAPID, maximum temperature: 100 °C; heating medium: water; total pots: 12; pot capacity: 250 ml each.) at the wet processing laboratory of the Textile Engineering Department, Northern University Bangladesh. The dyeing temperature was 60°C, and dyeing was carried out for about 90 minutes.

After dyeing, samples were washed at 40°C and soaped at 80°C for 15 minutes using 0.5 g/L ISO detergent. Later, samples were neutralized, squeezed and air-dried in a flat dryer machine. The reactive dyeing wastewater was collected directly from the dye bath before drainage. The following recipes were followed for the coloration of cotton in three different hues: navy, olive, and pale blue.

Table 2.1: Recipe for Navy

Dyes, Chemicals and dyeing parameters	Samples			
	Sample 01 (Navy)	Sample 02 (Navy)	Sample 03 (Navy)	Sample 04 (Navy)
Water type	Fresh water	Untreated reactive dyeing waste water		
Synozol Yellow K ₃ RS (owf)	0.493%	0.493%	0.493%	-
Synozol Red K ₃ BS (owf)	0.01%	0.01%	0.01%	-
Synozol Navy Blue KBF (owf)	2.991%	2.991%	2.991%	-
Glauber's salt	60g/L	60g/L	-	-
Soda ash	28g/L	28g/L	-	-
Wetting agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Sequestering agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Levelling agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Temperature	60°C			
Time	90mins			
pH	10-12			
M:L	1:10			

Table 2.2: Recipe for Olive

Dyes, Chemicals and dyeing parameters	Samples			
	Sample 01 (Olive)	Sample 02 (Olive)	Sample 03 (Olive)	Sample 04 (Olive)
Water type	Fresh water	Untreated reactive dyeing waste water		
Synozol Yellow K_3 RS (owf)	0.54%	0.54%	0.54%	-
Synozol Red K_3 BS (owf)	0.084%	0.084%	0.084%	-
Synozol Navy Blue KBF (owf)	0.28%	0.28%	0.28%	-
Glauber's salt	30g/L	30g/L	-	-
Soda ash	12g/L	12g/L	-	-
Wetting agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Sequestering agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Levelling agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Temperature	60°C			
Time	90mins			
pH	10-12			
M:L	1:10			

Table 2.3: Recipe for Pale blue

Dyes, Chemicals and dyeing parameters	Samples			
	Sample 01 (Pale blue)	Sample 02 (Pale blue)	Sample 03 (Pale blue)	Sample 04 (Pale blue)
Water type	Fresh water	Untreated reactive dyeing waste water		
Synozol Yellow K_3 RS (owf)	0.0423%	0.0423%	0.54%	-
Synozol Red K_3 BS (owf)	0.0216%	0.0216%	0.084%	-
Synozol Navy Blue KBF (owf)	0.1277%	0.1277%	0.28%	-
Glauber's salt	15g/L	15g/L	-	-
Soda ash	8g/L	8g/L	-	-
Wetting agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Sequestering agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Levelling agent	1g/L	1g/L	-	-
Temperature	60°C			
Time	90mins			
pH	10-12			
M:L	1:10			

Fig 2.1 Dyeing process curve

2.2.2 Determination of color difference (ΔE)

The color difference between freshwater-dyed samples and wastewater-dyed samples was measured by using a Datacolor spectrophotometer, considering the freshwater-dyed sample reading as standard for wastewater-dyed samples. Data for each sample were analysed with respect to color difference and ΔE value. ΔE is a single value that takes into account the differences between the L^* , a^* and b^* values of the sample and standard in the CIE $L^*a^*b^*$ color system. Equation 1 was used to calculate the ΔE value [24].

$$\Delta E = \sqrt{(L^*_2 - L^*_1)^2 + (a^*_2 - a^*_1)^2 + (b^*_2 - b^*_1)^2} \dots\dots\dots (1) [25]$$

Where, L^*_1 = Lightness of the standard sample, L^*_2 = lightness of the sample to be measured a^*_1 = Redness or greenness of the standard sample, a^*_2 = Redness or greenness of the sample to be measured, b^*_1 = yellowness or blueness of the standard sample, b^*_2 = yellowness or blueness of the sample to be measured.

2.2.3 Determination of colorfastness properties

The colorfastness properties of the freshwater and wastewater dyed samples were evaluated using the international test method provided by ISO Standard. Color fastness to wash, water, perspiration, rubbing, and light were conducted maintaining the ISO 105-C06:2010 [26], ISO 105-E01:2013 [27], ISO 105-E04:2013 [28], ISO105×12:2016 [29], and ISO 105 B06: 2020 [30] test procedure, respectively. Color fastness to wash, water, perspiration, and rubbing results were rated as per Grey scale for color change and Greyscale for color staining (rating 1-5, where 1 - poor, 2 - fair, 3 - good, 4 - very good and 5 -excellent)[31-33]. The color fastness to light properties of the samples were rated using the Blue wool scale with rating 1-8, where 1 - poor, 2 - fair, 3 -moderate, 4 - good, 5 - better, 6 - very good, 7 - best and 8 -excellent [30]. SDCE Multifibre DW (Acetate, Cotton, Nylon, Polyester, Acrylic and Wool) was used to test the fastness of the dyed samples.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Color difference (ΔE)

Table 3.1 Color difference values (Navy)

Sample name	ΔE	ΔL^*	Δa^*	Δb^*
Sample 01(Navy)		Consider as standard		
Sample 02(Navy)	0.94	0.20	0.46	0.81
Sample 03(Navy)	4.23	0.63	3.99	5.86
Sample 04(Navy)		No staining found		

Table 3.2 Color difference values (Olive)

Sample name	ΔE	ΔL^*	Δa^*	Δb^*
Sample 01(Olive)		Consider as standard		
Sample 02(Olive)	1.14	0.62	0.14	0.85
Sample 03(Olive)	1.23	0.47	0.02	0.90
Sample 04(Olive)		No staining found		

Table 3.3 Color difference values (Pale blue)

Sample name	ΔE	ΔL^*	Δa^*	Δb^*
Sample 01(Pale blue)		Consider as standard		
Sample 02(Pale blue)	0.47	0.70	0.31	0.04
Sample 03(Pale blue)	1.05	0.68	0.15	0.72
Sample 04 (Pale blue)		No staining found		

Tables 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 reported the color difference between wastewater-dyed samples (sample 02, sample 03, and sample 04) and freshwater-dyed samples (sample 01) for three different colors: navy, olive, and pale blue. For each color, we found the delta difference to be not more than ≤ 1.5 , except for sample 03 of the navy color. Other CMC values ΔL^* , Δa^* and Δb^* of freshwater-dyed samples and wastewater-dyed samples also showed a little difference in most cases. It resembles that regarding reactive

dyeing, we can use reactive dyeing wastewater directly to reuse the residual chemicals and water. However, sample 04 for each shade found no staining because this sample tried to dye using reactive dyeing wastewater without additional dyes or chemicals. As a result, hydrolysed reactive dye diffused a little into the fiber but could not bond with the fiber, and after soaping, all dyes were stripped from the surface [34].

Figure 3.1: Freshwater and wastewater dyed samples (Navy)

Figure 3.2: Freshwater and wastewater dyed samples (Olive)

Figure 3.3: Freshwater and wastewater dyed samples (Pale blue)

Figures 3.1, 3.2, and 3.3 showed the visual appearance of the freshwater and wastewater-dyed samples in different conditions for navy, olive, and pale blue colors. The results indicate that freshwater-dyed samples and wastewater-dyed samples with additional dyes, salt, and soda have similar appearances. However, sometimes wastewater-dyed samples with extra salt and soda can result in a darker shade. Sample 02 (Navy) appears darker visually, and it may be caused by the remaining salt and soda in the bath, which become higher in amount than freshwater after adding additional salt and soda.

Wastewater sample category 03 proved the effectiveness of the remaining salt and soda in the dye bath, though the color difference is higher than the sample category 2. In the case of sample category 04, only wastewater was used here to dye the fabric, and no staining was found after soaping because of the hydrolyzed dye in the bath. Due to the physical forces, hydrolyzed dye entered slightly into the fiber, but dyes were disporped or stripped out after soaping.

3.2 Color fastness to wash

Table 3.4 Color fastness to wash (Navy)

Sample name	Color change	Color staining					
		Acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Sample 01(Navy)	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Navy)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4	4	4
Sample 03(Navy)	4	4	4	4-5	4-5	4	4-5
Sample 04(Navy)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3.5 Color fastness to wash (Olive)

Sample name	Color change	Color staining					
		Acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Sample 01(Olive)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Olive)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03(Olive)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04(Olive)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3.6 Color fastness to wash (Pale blue)

Sample name	Color change	Color staining					
		Acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Sample 01(Pale blue)	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Pale blue)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03(Pale blue)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04(Pale blue)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Tables 3.4, 3.5, and 3.6 indicate the colorfastness to washing properties of freshwater and wastewater-dyed samples for navy, olive, and pale blue colors in various conditions. Almost overall colorfastness to wash results for color change and staining of all samples are very good to excellent. There is no such remarkable difference between freshwater and

wastewater-dyed samples. Regarding sample 04 for all colors, the results were excellent because no staining or color change happened due to their lack of dyes on it. So, largely reactive dyeing wastewater can be used directly to dye cotton fabric with reactive dye.

3.3 Color fastness to water

Table 3.7 Color fastness to water (Navy)

Sample name	Color change	Color staining					
		Acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Sample 01(Navy)	4	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Navy)	4	4	4	4-5	4	4	4
Sample 03(Navy)	4	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4	4-5
Sample 04(Navy)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3.8 Color fastness to water (Olive)

Sample name	Color change	Color staining					
		Acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Sample 01(Olive)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Olive)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03(Olive)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04(Olive)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3.9 Color fastness to water (Pale blue)

Sample name	Color change	Color staining					
		Acetate	Cotton	Nylon	Polyester	Acrylic	Wool
Sample 01(Pale blue)	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Pale blue)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03(Pale blue)	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04(Pale blue)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Tables 3.7, 3.8, and 3.9 illustrate the color fastness to water properties of different freshwater and wastewater-dyed samples for navy, olive, and pale blue colors. Both freshwater and wastewater dyed samples showed a very good to excellent greyscale rating. As there were no dyes in sample four, there was no staining, and the rating was either excellent or zero. Like color fastness to wash, similar results were found for freshwater dyed samples and reactive dyeing wastewater dyed samples, which indicates the favorability of reusing reactive dyeing wastewater for reactive coloration.

3.4 Color fastness to perspiration

Tables 3.10, 3.11, and 3.12 reported the color fastness to perspiration properties of freshwater-dyed and wastewater-dyed samples for navy, olive, and pale blue colors. For all samples, both in acidic and alkaline conditions, color change and color staining were very good to excellent. The grayscale rating indicates the superior fastness properties of reactive dyes. Here, no notable drawbacks or difficulties were found in using reactive dyeing wastewater for reactive coloration. As previously, due to the absence of dyes on sample four, not staining found and rated excellent. These results demonstrate the potential for directly reusing reactive dyeing wastewater in new dyeing processes.

Table 3.10 Color fastness to perspiration (Navy)

Sample name	Color change		Color staining												
			Acetate		Cotton		Nylon		Polyester		Acrylic		Wool		
	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	
Sample 01 (Navy)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02 (Navy)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03 (Navy)	4	4	4-5	4-5	3-4	3-4	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04 (Navy)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3.11 Color fastness to perspiration (Olive)

Sample name	Color change		Color staining												
			Acetate		Cotton		Nylon		Polyester		Acrylic		Wool		
	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	
Sample 01 (Olive)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02 (Olive)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03 (Olive)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04 (Olive)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 3.12 Color fastness to perspiration (Pale blue)

Sample name	Color change		Color staining												
			Acetate		Cotton		Nylon		Polyester		Acrylic		Wool		
	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	Acid	Alkali	
Sample 01 (Pale blue)	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 02 (Pale blue)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 03 (Pale blue)	4	4	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5	4-5
Sample 04 (Pale blue)	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

3.5 Color fastness to rubbing

Table 3.13 Color fastness to rubbing (Navy)

Sample name	Dry Rubbing	Wet rubbing
Sample 01(Navy)	4-5	3
Sample 02(Navy)	4-5	2-3
Sample 03(Navy)	4-5	2-3
Sample 04(Navy)	5	5

Table 3.14 Color fastness to rubbing (Olive)

Sample name	Dry Rubbing	Wet rubbing
Sample 01(Olive)	4-5	4
Sample 02(Olive)	4-5	4
Sample 03(Olive)	4-5	4
Sample 04(Olive)	5	5

Table 3.15 Color fastness to rubbing (Pale blue)

Sample name	Dry Rubbing	Wet rubbing
Sample 01(Pale blue)	4-5	4-5
Sample 02(Pale blue)	4-5	4-5
Sample 03(Pale blue)	4-5	4
Sample 04(Pale blue)	5	5

Tables 3.13, 3.14, and 3.15 exhibited the color fastness to rubbing properties of the freshwater-dyed samples and wastewater-dyed samples for the navy, olive, and pale blue colors. In general, both freshwater and wastewater-dyed samples provided very good to excellent color fastness for rubbing. However, for navy color, samples one, two, and three showed slightly poorer results than olive and pale blue colors. It may be caused by the higher shade percentage of navy color and the unexhausted dye on the surface, but it yielded similar results both for freshwater and wastewater-dyed samples. That specifies that, as a dyeing media, reactive dyeing wastewater can be used directly for the reactive dyeing of cotton without any significant difficulties. Sample four remained unchanged due to the absence of dyes

3.6 Color fastness to light

Table 3.16 Color fastness to light

Sample name	Navy	Olive	Pale blue
Sample 01	5	4	4
Sample 02	4	4	4
Sample 03	4	3	3
Sample 04	8	8	8

Table 3.16 denotes the color fastness to light results of freshwater-dyed and wastewater-dyed samples for navy, olive, and pale blue colors. All samples showed a fair to moderate blue wool scale rating on average, while the navy color reached moderate-to-good for all samples. However, olive and pale blue showed fair to moderate ratings. Considering the dyeing medium, additional dyes and chemicals, wastewater-dyed samples with only the additional dyes yielded a lower rating than any other samples. In sample four, as there was no dye, there was no fading, and the results were outstanding.

In a nutshell, the color difference of the freshwater-dyed and wastewater-dyed samples was within the tolerable limit, and the serviceability properties of both samples have no distinct difference, except the light fastness properties of wastewater-dyed samples. Additionally, this study found no significant difficulties in directly reusing reactive dyeing wastewater for the reactive coloration of cotton.

4. Conclusion

The feasibility of reusing reactive dyeing wastewater for the reactive coloration of cotton and the performance of the dyed samples have been investigated. The outcomes of the study demonstrated that reactive dyeing wastewater can be directly reused in the reactive coloration of cotton without impacting the shades and serviceability properties of the dyed samples. The freshwater-dyed and wastewater-dyed samples showed no noticeable difference, considering shades and fastness properties.

Thus, the study's findings will open a new window for reusing and recycling reactive dyeing wastewater for textile coloration to save the world from the excessive use of freshwater. Not only it will reduce freshwater consumption, but also reduce chemical usages and dyeing costs by reusing residual chemicals. Simultaneously, the environmental hazard can be eliminated significantly by using less freshwater and residual chemicals and generating less influent.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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